

MOLDING AND MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF FIBER BRAIDS RODS

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Abstract

Steel rebar has been used for hundreds of years as the reinforcement of concrete structures. But as the increasing special needs, non-magnetism, non-conductivity and non-corrosive for example, traditional concrete structure can't satisfy the need of special facilities. The most effective way to solve the problem is the steel replacement by other ideal materials, such as fiber-reinforced-polymer (FRP) composites.

In this study, three kinds of ideal fiber with superior mechanical properties were used to braid in the same way into ropes, which would be made into rods after being impregnated, pushed and stiffed through the pultrusion process.

Mechanical properties including, tensile strength and maximum load-were tested to check the quality level of the fabricated rods., The mechanical capacities of the three rods through same fabricate process are below expectation in this study. Further works of research should be made effect to do in the field of fundamental rope.

Keywords: *rod; unsaturated resin; molding; mechanical properties*

1 Introduction

Braiding has been used for making textile structure for thousand years such as ropes and shoelaces. Hundreds of braided products exist with the development of technology, including reinforcement for hydraulic hoses, electromagnetic shielding, shoelaces, sutures, mountain climbing ropes, braids of resorbable materials for medical applications, hydraulic hoses, tethers for offshore oil platforms, airbeams for tents, composite preforms for bicycle frames, skiis, skateboards and hockey sticks[1]. For the past few years, as a technological means for manufacturing preforms for composite structures, braiding has been drawing a great deal of attention[2-5]. At present braiding rods impregnated with unsaturated resin are used as reinforcement and also as tension cables of concrete structures in Japan. As reinforcement of concrete structures, instead of steel rebar, it has some special features such as non-magnetism, lightweight,

non-conductivity and non-corrosive. Since it was used in the shape of braided rod as tension cables of PC bridge for the first time in 1990, it has been used for PC structures, such as floating bridges, girders, floor slabs and railway sleepers. And it has also been used for advanced research facilities which require non-magnetism and non-conductivity.

Braided fabric is a great candidate for reinforcement of composite materials. Composite structure reinforced with braided fabrics has lots of advantages over other competing structures such as filament wound composites and woven [6]. The superior characteristic of braided composites is the continuity of the fiber bundles through the composite in any kind of shape. For this reason, every fiber can sustain applied load and this mechanism, consequently, brings about high-performance composites. On the other hand, braiding has a potential for use in continuous

manufacturing processes -- the braiding pultrusion process (BPP), for example.

2 Material and Experiment

2.1 Fiber and Unsaturated Resin

In this study, three kinds of ideal fiber with superior mechanical properties, basalt fiber (produced by Zhejiang GBF Basalt Fiber Co., LTD.), carbon fiber (produced by WEI HAI TUO ZHAN CO., LTD.) and aramid fiber (produced from Dupont co.), were investigated and unsaturated polyester resin was used as matrix owing to its availability, low price, and high hardening activity. The specifications of the three kinds of fiber and the unsaturated resin are summarized in Table 1.

2.2 Braiding process

As we all know, braiding method has been used for manufacturing textile structure for thousand years such as ropes and shoelaces. For the past few years, as a technological means for making preforms for composite structures, braiding has been drawing a great deal of attention. Braids can provide

Fig.1. Double-six strands braiding rope model

The facades of the three braided ropes show in Fig3. The carbon and basalt rope with non-smooth surfaces have unstable braiding pitch. The broken fibers in the appearance of the rope can be seen easily. The hand handle is stiff and tight. On the

continuous bundle arrangement in the axial direction and can bear the axial loads with all the bundles [7]. Different braiding methods result in different cable structures leading to different mechanical properties.

In this study, an traditional but useful technology was accepted and one kind of shape (Fig 1) manufactured by three materials, carbon fibers, aramid fibers and basalt fibers, was researched. This structure was created on braiding machine, where two sets of packages (spools or bobbins) on carriers move on a circular track with a similar sinusoidal oscillation, one set consisting of three groups of bobbins moving clockwise and the other three groups of bobbins counterclockwise, and driven by a circular spur gear train[1]. The moving trail of the bobbins illustrates in the Fig2. The clockwise moving packages and the counterclockwise moving packages interlace with each other. The formed braided rope is pulled through a guide hole and then rolled onto a motor-driven reel.

Fig.2. Illustration of standard braiding process using horn gears

other hand, the appearance of aramid rope is smoother than the other two ropes. However, the trace of each tow of fiber can be easily observed in the axial direction, which has tight relationship with the space between fiber bundles.

(a) The carbon rope

(b) The basalt rope

(c) The aramid rope

Fig.3. The appearance of the ropes

2.3 Braiding Pultrusion Process (BPP)

The combination processes of braiding and pultrusion has been also named pull-braiding, braided-pultrusion and braidtrusion in different works [6]. Pultrusion is a continuous process for manufacture of composite materials with constant cross-section (Fig4). The process begins when ropes, which are braided in double-six braiding ways (Fig1), are pulled from a series of creels. The ropes proceed through a bath, where they are impregnated with unsaturated polyester resin. The resin-impregnated ropes are preformed to the shape of the profile to be produced. This composite material is then passed through a heated steel die that has been machined precisely to the final shape of the part to be manufactured.

Heat initiates an exothermic reaction thus curing the thermosetting resin matrix. The profile is continuously pulled and exits the mould as a hot, constant cross sectional member. The profile cools in ambient or forced air, or assisted by water. The product emerges from the puller mechanical and is cut to the desired length by an automatic, flying

cutoff saw [8]. Fig5 shows the finished specimens through the above process.

Fig.4. Schematic illustration of pultrusion process

3 Experimental testing

The basic arguments of the specimens list in table.2, which include nominal diameters, cross section and unit mass. For measuring accurately, water gaging method was accepted to get the volume. Then the unit mass of the materials could be calculated precisely. Fig6 shows the process of the specimens during testing experiments.

Several kinds of braided pultruded process (BPP) rods were investigated containing several sample types that qualified the effect of materials.

Fig.5. The finished composite rods by the BPP process

(a) Mass measuring

(b) Volume measuring

Fig6. The measuring of the unit mass

For measuring tensile strength, max load and other physical capabilities of manufactured rods, every kind of the three specimens was well prepared for tensile test. Each type of those rods was cut into

pieces of 500 mm and two ends of all samples were reinforced by tailor-made collet (see Fig7) to increase the friction force and decrease the slippage during tensile test.

Fig.7. The specimens before testing

4 Results and Discussions

Figure.8 shows the specimens after tensile test. The table.3 shows the appearances and fundamental parameters of the ropes. The surfaces of the ropes are not smooth enough (see Fig.3) owing to the superabundant friction with the braiding machine and overlarge bending tensile force in the braiding machine. At the same time, all those non-ideal

factors lead to the fracture of the fibers exposed in the surface of the ropes, which decrease the physical performances of the rope drastically. On the other hand, the unstable drafting force of the braiding machine contributes to the instability of the pitch of the braiding ropes, especially, the aramid ropes, the pitch range of which is from 131 to 169 mm.

Table 4-6 show the fundamental geometry and mechanical arguments of various specimens. The average maximum tensile load of the three kinds of composite materials, carbon fiber, aramid fiber and basalt fiber composites, are 122.3kN, 95.8kN and 98.5kN separately. The tensile strengths of the rods are 923 kN/mm², 1508 kN/mm² and 1176 kN/mm² respectively. Obviously, the mechanical properties of the carbon rods and the basalt rods are below expectation based on the present situation. On the

other hand, the aramid rods meet the request of the theoretical load value, the excellent abrasive resistance and deflection are the most important factors for meeting the requirement. It is worth mentioning that the kelter fiber was produced from Dupont co., in this view, the quality of carbon and basalt fibers is another of the most important elements for which affect the mechanical properties of the rods.

Fig.8. The specimens after testing

From another point of view, the unstable drafting force and superabundant friction with the machine not only led to the non-ideal appearance quality, but also contributed to the brittle of the fibers, which brought defects of rope structure. Consequently, the mechanical properties of ropes were severely weakened.

5 Conclusions

In this study, three kinds of fibers were chosen as the reinforcement of the composite and unsaturated polyester resin was used as matrix. The ropes were braided in double-six braiding way and then the ropes were made into the tubes through the BPP process.

The mechanical properties of the carbon rods and the basalt rods are below expectation. Even though the aramid rods meet the request of the theoretical load value, the material is made in Japan, which means the composite rods still have a long way to go in China. From the raw material to the braiding structure, plying method to forming process, the research of every step of the whole process needs to work on.

From above work, we can see that it is hard to fabricate the composite rods with high properties as Japan's under present conditions. The quality of raw material can't improve by large percentage in the short-term. In this case, the first step of the future work is going to do some fundamental research on the braiding ropes.

Various braiding structures will be taken into considerations. Different braiding methods result in different cable structures leading to different mechanical properties. The double-eight strands braiding, for example, will be researched in details. Great attention should also be paid to the way of plying of the strands. Combination is going to be

made in the braiding process or before the braiding process. The interstices between the yarns, which can be effected by the style of combination, have an effect on the properties of the ropes and the rods.

Table.1
Parameters of mechanical properties of ropes

Type	Density (g/cm ³)	Moisture percentage (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Breaking elongation (%)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Diameter (μ m)	Linear density (tex)
Kevlar49	1.45	3.5	3000	2.4	112.4	-	-
Carbon	1.78	-	4100	1.72	238	6.9	796
Basalt	-	< 0.100	-	-	-	9	800

Table2.
The arguments of the fabricated specimens

Type	Nominal diameter (mm)	Cross section (mm ²)	Unit mass (m/g)
Carbon	12.99	132.51	206.1
Aramid	9.00	63.54	81.9
Basalt	10.33	83.77	184.2

Table.3
Appearances and fundamental arguments of the ropes

Number	Raw material	Mass(g/m)	Pitch(mm)	Core(mm)	Appearance
A	Aramid	67.1	131-169	None	Multiple loop, set pitch instability
B	Basalt	168.5	123-125	None	Multiple loop, multiple broken filament,
C	Carbon	175.3	127-134	None	Multiple broken filament

Table.4
The arguments of aramid rods

Type	Nominal diameter (mm)	Cross section (mm ²)	Unit mass (m/g)	Max load (kN)	Tensile strength (kN/mm ²)	Specific ratio to the contrast strength (%)
A-1	8.99	63.39	81.7	98.0	1,546	115
A-2	9.02	63.84	82.2	100.0	1,566	118
A-3	8.99	63.39	81.9	89.5	1,421	105
Average	9.00	63.54	81.9	95.8	1,508	113

Table.5

The arguments of basalt rods

Type	Nominal diameter (mm)	Cross section (mm ²)	Unit mass (m/g)	Max load (kN)	Tensile strength (kN/mm ²)	Specific ratio to the contrast strength (%)
Ba-1	10.27	82.82	182.9	99.0	1,195	-
Ba-2	10.36	84.28	184.5	92.0	1,092	-
Ba-3	10.36	84.20	185.1	104.5	1,241	-
Average	10.33	83.77	184.2	98.5	1,176	-

Table.6

The arguments of carbon rods

Type	Nominal diameter (mm)	Cross section (mm ²)	Unit mass (m/g)	Max load (kN)	Tensile strength (kN/mm ²)	Specific ratio to the contrast strength (%)
C-1	13.06	133.89	206.6	114.0	851	43
C-2	12.92	131.13	204.5	132.0	1,007	50
C-3	12.99	132.51	207.3	121.0	913	46
Average	12.99	132.51	206.1	122.3	923	46

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